

Lectio Divina for the Time of COVID-19

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A *re you serving directly in this fight to save the humanity?
You are, of course, engaged fully.
Just keep in your heart, "God, be in me, and be with us"*

*Are you locked down at home?
There is a long time to pass
Alone, away, constrained, concerned...
Pass over gracefully.*

See well
The News, the updates, instructions, orders ...
The sick, the abandoned, the dying, the people in healthcare,
the fleeing migrants,
Read their pain, fear, hunger, health, fatigue,

Our own people - spouse, parents, children, friends...
There are lots of things to read attentively in them,
Which we never gave attention;
their love, likes, desires, complaints, silence...

See well the world, society, the poor, caretakers, the police,
the government...
Read attentively, the many cares that we took for granted.

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See well the nature, the plants,
the animals, the air, the
water,
Read attentively the mysteries
we desacralized

Feel them
Feel what is seen and read,
Imagine the path they walk, hold
their pain, rejection,
neglect, struggle, fatigue,
fear ...

Express
Express them in gestures, sighs, or even in words,
Your heart might whisper just a word, 'O God.'
It is your sincere cry that involves your prayer for them,
repentance for what is neglected, gratitude for what is
seen as received.

Hear
Hear the voice of God, speaking to you and the whole of what
you have seen, read, felt and voiced.
Feel the consolation, comfort, and the presence of God for you
and for the world,
in hospitals, in streets, with the sick and the dying, with the
caretakers and the scientists, with the police and the
governments.
Firmly believe the presence of God, not just for your protection
and care, but all the more the presence with the sick and
the dying.
You could see the presence of God as a guest and a host within
the locked down house.
Since it is simple, it might be hard to practice.

**It might also fill you
with compassion,
tenderness, and
courage.
There will be healing,
miracle, and
reconciliation.**

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Make an attempt
trusting in grace
It might also fill you
with compassion,
tenderness, and
courage.
There will be healing,
miracle, and reconciliation.

LECTIO DIVINA
Reading the Scripture
Reflecting on the Meaning
Responding through Prayer
Resting in God
Responding in Action

Lectio Meditatio Oratio Contemplatio Operatio

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